

A Study on Complex Formation of Beryllium with Salicylic and Sulphosalicylic Acids

Rebati Charan Das and S. Aditya

Beryllium perchlorate (Be^{2+}) forms a colorless complex with salicylic acid as well as with sulphosalicylic acid. The nature of these complexes has been studied by ultraviolet spectrophotometry. The absorption spectra at different pH's suggest that the complex formation increases with an increase in pH. Composition of these complexes has been studied at pH 4.5 by Job's method of continued variation. The molecular ratio of Be^{2+} to the ligand in both the complexes is 1:1. Stability constants have been determined at ionic strengths 0.02, 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2M for the Be^{2+} -salicylic acid complex as well as for the Be^{2+} -sulphosalicylic acid complex. Thermodynamic stability constants have been found by extrapolation and are 1.66×10^4 and 2.24×10^4 for salicylic acid and sulphosalicylic acid complexes respectively; the values of $-\Delta F^\circ$ are 5830 and 6010 cal. respectively.

Meeks and Bank (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4108) studied spectrophotometrically the complex formed by Be^{2+} with sulphosalicylic acid at pH 4.5. Verma and Mehrotra (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 380) studied the nature of beryllium-salicylic acid complex by electrometric and conductometric titrations. In the present work the nature of the complexes formed by beryllium with salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids has been investigated spectrophotometrically at a lower pH range; the stability constants have also been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Beryllium perchlorate was prepared by dissolving B.D.H. beryllium carbonate in pure perchloric acid solution. Sufficient free acid was present in the solution to prevent hydrolysis of the metal ion. Beryllium content was estimated by precipitating the hydroxide and subsequently heating it to oxide (Vogel, "Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 2nd ed., p. 450).

Both salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids were of E. Merck G. R. quality. The stock solutions were prepared by dissolving in double-distilled water and were estimated by titration against standard alkali. Sodium perchlorate (B.D.H.) was used to maintain the ionic strength. All other chemicals were of Reagent grade.

The solutions for the measurements were prepared by taking required volumes of beryllium perchlorate and the ligand solutions from the stock. Requisite amounts of alkali or acid and sodium perchlorate were added before dilution to maintain the pH and the ionic strength respectively in the same way as reported earlier (Das and Aditya, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 557).

Absorbancies were measured with a Hilger-Watt 'Uvispek' spectrophotometer, model H 700/303, using quartz cells of 10 mm path length. Duplicate readings were taken for each solution by taking measurements with cells interchanged. The slit width was adjusted corresponding to a band width of 5 Å. The pH measurements were made with a Marconi pH meter, model TF 511 D. The experiments were done at room temperature, which varied between 28° and 32°.

DISCUSSION

Salicylic acid has an absorption maximum at 296 m μ . The addition of beryllium perchlorate shifts the maximum to 305 m μ at pH 4.5. A similar shift from 297 m μ to 304 m μ was also observed with sulphosalicylic acid. Figure 1 shows the absorption curves of salicylic acid at pH 3.0 and 4.5 and those of a solution of salicylic acid and beryllium ion at the same pH values. pH 4.5 was thus chosen for further work.

Composition of the Complexes

For determination of molecular composition of the complexes Job's method of continued variation (*Compt. rend.*, 1928, 180, 928; *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113) was used. Figure 2 represents the continued variation curve for Be^{2+} -salicylic acid system. At wave length 315 $m\mu$ the curve passes through a maximum, while at 285 $m\mu$ it passes through a minimum. Both the curves indicate a complex between Be^{2+} and salicylic acid in the ratio of 1:1. The curves at wave lengths 310 $m\mu$ and 320 $m\mu$ also have the maximum at the molecular ratio of 1:1. In the case of sulphosalicylic acid system, the continued variation curve passes through a minimum at the wave length 285 $m\mu$ and maxima at other three wave lengths. In this case also the molecular ratio of beryllium to the ligand in the complex is 1:1 at the above pH. That not more than one complex is formed at pH 4.5 is assumed from the fact that the maxima or minima of the Job's curves remain unchanged at all wave lengths (Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 487).

FIG. 1

Curves I & II—Actual % T = % T from graph (pH 4.5)
Curves III & IV—Actual % T = % T from graph -20 (pH 3.0)

FIG. 2

Extinction Coefficient

Extinction coefficients of the beryllium complexes were determined by measuring optical densities of the solutions at wave length 315 $m\mu$ and at pH 4.5, with beryllium ion concentrations in 20 to 30 folds excess, when the complex formation was assumed to be complete and the absorbancies were entirely due to the complexes formed. The values for the extinction coefficients of Be^{2+} -salicylic acid and Be^{2+} -sulphosalicylic acid complexes at pH 4.5 and at wave length 315 $m\mu$ were found to be 4468 ± 12 and 3996 ± 5 respectively as against 1184 ± 2.6 and 984 ± 1.3 respectively for the ligands.

Stability Constants

For determination of stability constants, absorbancies of the solutions containing beryllium perchlorate and the ligand, with pH adjusted to 4.5, were measured at wave length 315 m μ . Requisite amounts of sodium perchlorate were added to these to fix the ionic strengths. The ionic strength was calculated from the amount of sodium perchlorate added as the concentration was large in comparison with that of any other constituent in the solution. Calculation of the stability constant was done in the following manner.

At pH 4.5, both the ligands, salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids, exist in the form :

(which is represented as HR). The reaction equilibrium can then be represented as :

At constant H^+ -ion concentration,

$$\frac{[\text{BeR}]}{[\text{Be}^{2+}] [\text{HR}]}$$

is a constant (K). The concentration of $[\text{HR}]$ is equal to $[\text{HR}]_T - [\text{BeR}]$, where $[\text{HR}]_T$ is the total concentration of the ligand and $[\text{BeR}]$ is the concentration of the ligand bound in the complex. Similarly, the concentration of the free beryllium ion is given by $[\text{Be}^{2+}]_T - [\text{BeR}]$. Thus the association constant is given by the expression :

$$K = \frac{[\text{BeR}]}{\{[\text{Be}^{2+}]_T - [\text{BeR}]\} \{[\text{HR}]_T - [\text{BeR}]\}}$$

The concentration of the complex, *i.e.*, $[\text{BeR}]$ in the above equation, is calculated from the optical density of the solution containing Be^{2+} ion and the ligand, using the expression,

$$\text{Optical density} = \epsilon_2 [\text{BeR}] l + \epsilon_1 \{[\text{HR}]_T - [\text{BeR}]\} l,$$

where ϵ_2 and ϵ_1 are the extinction coefficients of the complex and the ligand respectively and ' l ', the cell width.

At each ionic strength ten sets of optical density measurements were taken with solutions containing different amounts of the metal ion and the ligand. The number of measurements taken and the average association constants with standard deviations from the same are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Stability constant of Be-salicylic acid and Be-sulphosalicylic acid complexes.
pH = 4.5. No. of readings taken with varying conc. of Be and ligand = 10.

Ionic strength.	Mean value of $K \times 10^{-4}$ for the complex with	
	Salicylic acid.	Sulphosalicylic acid.
0.02	1.205 $\pm$ 0.11	1.960 $\pm$ 0.20
0.05	1.008 $\pm$ 0.09	1.715 $\pm$ 0.17
0.10	0.937 $\pm$ 0.07	1.501 $\pm$ 0.18
0.20	0.900 $\pm$ 0.09	1.470 $\pm$ 0.15

An analysis of the results shows that with an increase in the ionic strength the stability constant decreases.

For calculation of the thermodynamic association constants, the values of the activity coefficients of different species in solution are necessary. Since it is difficult to determine them experimentally and also it is not possible to get them theoretically, the thermodynamic association constants (K_T) have been found by extrapolating the curve ($\log K$ against ionic strength) to zero ionic strength. The values of K_T 's for the salicylic and sulphosalicylic acid complexes of beryllium are 1.66×10^4 and 2.24×10^4 respectively. Taking the average temperature (at which the experiments were done) to be $30^\circ \pm 2^\circ$, the values of $-\Delta F$'s for the complexes were calculated. For the Be^{2+} —salicylic acid complex, it is 5830 cal. and for the Be^{2+} —sulphosalicylic acid complex, it is 6010 cal.

As can be observed from the values of stability constants, sulphosalicylic acid forms a stronger complex with beryllium ion than salicylic acid. Similar observations were made by us in connection with our studies on complexes of Al^{3+} , Ca^{2+} , and Fe^{3+} (unpublished).

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MAYURBHANJ CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
RAVENSHAW COLLEGE, CUTTACK-3.

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